

Chemical constituents of *Coriaria nepalensis* Wall.

N. P. Rai^a, K. Masuda^b and M. D. Manandhar^{a*}

^aCentral Department of Chemistry, Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Nepal

^bShowa Pharmaceutical University, Machida, Tokyo-194-8543, Japan

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Isolation of known compounds hexacosyl-*p*-coumarate, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid and stigmaterol glucoside and bryonolic acid have been reported for the first time from the aerial parts of *Coriaria nepalensis* Wall.

Coriaria nepalensis Wall.¹ (*Coriariaceae*) locally recognized in Nepal as *Bhojinsi* or *Machhaino* is a food plant for silk moth, *Actias selene* Hubn. Fruits of the plant though normally edible cause colic on excess consumption. Leaves, if fed to cattle in large doses, are poisonous.

Coriose², ellagic acid³, teetin⁴, epibryonolic acid³ and coriarin⁵ from different species of *Coriaria* have been reported. (*R*)-13-Hydroxy-*cis*-9-*trans*-11-octadecadienoic acid⁶ from fruits, coriose⁷ from leaves, and braylin, norbraylin, dihydrocoriamyrtin, coriamyrtin, futin, coriatin, apotutin, hydroxycoriatin and gallic acid⁸ from root of *C. nepalensis* (*Coriaria sinica* Maxim.) were reported.

Methanol extract of *C. nepalensis* Wall. has shown strong cytotoxic (*Artemia salina*), strong molluscicidal, mild anthelmintic, and weak hemolytic activities. The ethyl acetate extract was found to have strong cytotoxic, antibacterial, antifungal, and nematocidal (*Meloidognyne incognita*) activities. Petroleum ether extract has shown cytotoxic, nematocidal, and antibacterial activities.

Shade dried and powdered aerial parts of the plant (1.9 kg) were extracted successively with hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol in Soxhlet extractor. The hexane extract (10.0 g) on chromatography over silica gel column gave compound **1** (hexacosyl-*p*-coumarate) (0.060 g). Ethyl acetate extracts (4.25 g) on repeated chromatography afforded compound **2** (oleanolic acid) (0.028 g) and compound **3** (bryonolic acid) (0.046 g). The chloroform extract (6.93 g) was subjected to vacuum liquid chromatography followed by column chromatography, which yielded compound **4** (ursolic acid) (0.018 g), and compound **5** (stigmaterol glucoside) (0.015 g).

Compound **1**, C₃₅H₆₀O₃, a white amorphous compound, m.p. 80°C (lit.⁹ m.p. 95–96°C) gave positive test with ferric chloride for phenolic group. *m/z* (%): [M⁺], 528 (24), 500

(60), 472 (17), 164 (base peak), 147 (73) and 120 (30); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3399 (-OH), 1674 (conjugated >C=O), 1602, 1516 cm⁻¹ (aromatic nucleus); δ_{H} (CDCl₃/1 drop CD₃OD, 399.65 MHz) 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz, H-1'), 7.41 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-3, H-5), 6.83 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-2, H-6), 6.28 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz, H-2'), 4.20 (2H, t, *J* 6.72 Hz, -CO-O-CH₂-), 1.60–1.71 (6H, m, CH₂ × 3), 1.25 (1H, bs, -OH) and 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₃). A pair of doublets observed in its ¹H NMR spectrum at δ 7.62 and 6.28 was assigned for two olefinic protons (H-1' and H-2') at α and β positions to the carbonyl group. It is further confirmed by its ¹H-¹H COSY and HMBC spectra. The carbonyl carbon showed a multiple bond correlation with the methylene protons at 4.19 showing the presence of carbonyl group adjacent to oxygen, which in turn should be attached to methylene group. ¹³C NMR, DEPT (CDCl₃/1 drop CD₃OD, 100.40 MHz) δ 167.75 (ester carbonyl), 158.50 (C-1), 144.50 (C-1'), 115.74 (C-2), 115.10 (C-2'), 129.88 (C-3), 126.50 (C-4), 129.88 (C-5), 115.74 (C-6), 64.59 (-CO-O-CH₂), 32.00 to 22.50 (24 methylene carbons) and 14.05 (CH₃). The compound **1** was identified as hexacosyl-*p*-coumarate on the basis of its ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, DEPT, mass spectral data analysis as well as by study of its ¹H and ¹³C data of its methyl ether and acetyl derivatives⁹.

Compound **2**, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, M⁺ 456, an amorphous compound, m.p. 288°C, (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 288–290°C) gave positive Liebermann Buchard test for triterpene. ν_{\max} (KBr) 3434 (-OH), 1688 (-COOH), 1594, 1465, 1384, 1353 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃/1 drop CD₃OD, 399.65 MHz) 5.28 (1H, dd, *J* 3.40, 3.40 Hz, H-12), 3.21 (1H, dd, *J* 11.30, 4.70 Hz, α H-3), 2.83 (1H, dd, *J* 13.70, 4.0 Hz, β H-18), 1.52 (1H, H-9), 1.14 (3H, s, H-27), 0.98 (3H, s, H₃-23), 0.93 (3H, s, H₃-30), 0.91 (3H, s, H₃-25), 0.90 (3H, s, H-29), 0.77 (6H, s, H₃-24, H₃-26) and 0.72 (H, H-5). The compound was identified as oleanolic acid by comparing its EIMS, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR,

DEPT data with that of the reported values¹¹ as well as by direct comparison (co-tlc, m.m.p.) with an authentic compound and preparation of its acetyl derivative.

Compound 3, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, (M⁺ 456), a white amorphous compound, m.p. 276°C (lit.¹² m.p. 276–277°C) gave positive tests for triterpene and acidic functional group. *m/z* (%) M⁺ 456 (54), 441 (42), 423 (24), 368 (5), 259 (56), 247 (39), 235 (35), 229 (29), 203 (22), and 189 (23); δ_H (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz) 4.29 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, -OH), 2.97 (1H, m, H-3), 2.28 (2H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz, H-19), 1.09 (3H, s, H₃-29), 0.98 (3H, s, H₃-28), 0.91 (3H, s, H₃-26), 0.88 (3H, s, H₃-23), 0.87 (3H, s, H₃-25), 0.84 (3H, s, H₃-27) and 0.67 (3H, s, H₃-24). The ¹³C NMR showed signals for a total thirty carbons which were resolved into seven methyls, eleven methylenes and three methines on the basis of its DEPT spectrum. ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 125.65 MHz) δ 34.67 (C-1), 27.63 (C-2), 76.76 (C-3), 38.43 (C-4), 50.18 (C-5), 18.83 (C-6), 27.09 (C-7), 133.28 (C-8), 133.37 (C-9), 37.09 (C-10), 20.17 (C-11), 29.79 (C-12), 36.67 (C-13), 41.35 (C-14), 24.52 (C-15), 36.67 (C-16), 30.53 (C-17), 44.15 (C-18), 29.95 (C-19), 39.50 (C-20), 28.96 (C-21), 33.94 (C-22), 28.13 (C-23), 16.06 (C-24), 19.67 (C-25), 21.82 (C-26), 17.27 (C-27), 30.99 (C-28), 32.50 (C-29) and 179.55 (C-30). On the basis of spectral comparison of the parent compound and its acetyl derivative with literature^{13,14}, it was identified as bryonolic acid.

Compound 4, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, a white amorphous, m.p. 236°C (lit.¹⁵ 240–242°C), gave positive test for triterpenes. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 500, MHz) δ 5.24 (1H, t, *J* 3.75 Hz, H-12), 3.20 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0, 8.0 Hz, H-3), 2.20 (1H, d, *J* 11.0 Hz, H-18), 1.09 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 0.94 (3H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 0.92 (3H, s), 0.86 (3H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 0.81 (3H, s) and 0.78 (3H, s). The compound was identified as ursolic acid (m.m.p. and co-tlc with authentic sample).

Compound 5, C₃₅H₅₈O₆, a white amorphous powder, m.p. 274°C (dec.), *R*_f 0.54 (methanol : ethyl acetate, 1 : 4) gave positive test for glycoside. *m/z* 597 (M + Na)⁺, 395, 181, 152 (base peak), 139, 136 and 43; ν_{max} (KBr) 3400, 2962, 2950, 1460, 1380, 1370, 1060 and 1020 cm⁻¹; δ_H (pyridine, 500 MHz) 5.36 (1H, bs, H-6), 5.23 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7, 15.1 Hz, H-22), 5.08 (1H, dd, *J* 8.9, 15.1 Hz, H-23), 5.06 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5, 11.0 Hz, H-1'), 4.60 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0, 2.5 Hz, H-6'a), 4.45 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0, 4.5 Hz, H-6'b), 4.32 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0, 9.0 Hz, H-2'), 4.29 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5, 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 4.07 (1H, dd, *J* 8.25, 9.0 Hz, H-4'), 4.01 (2H, m, H₃, H-5'), 1.09 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, H₃-21), 0.95 (3H, s, H₃-19), 0.92 (3H, d, *J*

6.5 Hz, H₃-26 or 27), 0.89 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, H₃-29), 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H₃-26 or 27) and 0.68 (3H, s, H₃-18). The compound was identified as stigmasterol 3-*O*-β-D-gluopyrano-side (m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc with the authentic sample).

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References

1. 'Medicinal Plants of Nepal'. Published by HMG, Department of Medicinal Plants, Thapathali, Kathmandu, Nepal, 1970, 109.
2. T. Okuda and M. Hayashi, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, **16**, 601.
3. Y. S. Chang, M. S. Lin, R. L. Giang, S. C. Huang and L. K. Ho, *Phytochemistry*, 1966, **42**, 559.
4. G. Aguirre, E. Luis and W. Templeton, *Planta Med.*, 1990, **56**, 244.
5. T. Hatano, R. Yoshihara, S. Hattori, M. Yashizaki, Y. Shingu and T. Okuda, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1992, **40**, 1703; W. H. Tallent, J. Harris and I. A. Wolff, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, **36**, 4329.
6. W. H. Tallent, J. Harris and I. A. Wolff, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, **36**, 4329.
7. T. Okuda and M. Hayashi, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, **16**, 601.
8. W. Hong, Z. Fanjan, L. Miny and T. Renjiu, *Yaoyue Xuebo*, 1998, **33**, 688.
9. A. Chatterjee, S. K. Saha and S. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 421.
10. S. Ahmed and M. Ikram, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 2542.
11. K. Tori, S. Seo, A. Shimaoka and Y. Tomita, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, **48**, 4227.
12. K. Y. Sim and H. T. Lee, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 3342.
13. C. N. Lin, M. I. Chung and J. R. Chiang, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 2384.
14. W. Kamisako, K. Suwa, C. Honda, K. Isoi, H. Nakai, H. Shiro and K. Machida, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1987, **25**, 848.
15. F. H. Reginatto, C. Kaufmanns, J. Schripoema, D. Guillaume and G. Gasmann, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **12**, 35.